

Smart Dustbin monitoring and alert system using IOT

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Abstract- This paper proposes a smart bin system that uses Internet of Things (IOT) to monitor the garbage level in urban areas. The system consists of sensors that measure the fill level of the garbage bins and send the data to a cloud server. The server analyzes the data and notifies the municipality when the garbage bins are about to overflow, so that they can be cleared in time. This way, the system prevents pollution problems caused by overfilled garbage bins and helps the nearby residents to keep their environment clean. The paper also discusses the design, implementation and evaluation of the smart bin system and its benefits for waste management.

Index Terms- smartbin, Internet of Things, garbage, cloud server, waste management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Now-a-days urbanization and population growth pose significant challenges for waste management in urban areas. When garbage bins are overflowing, they create environmental hazards such as soil, water and air pollution. Moreover, some people dispose of hazardous waste such as batteries, e-waste and medical waste inappropriately, which can contaminate the soil and groundwater and affect the health of nearby residents. Therefore, it is essential to adopt effective and sustainable waste management practices to protect the environment and public health. Effective waste management has become a critical issue for towns and local governments in today's world of rapidly urbanizing populations. Cities are becoming more and more populated, which increases the amount of waste produced and calls for creative ways to streamline the waste collection process. In order to handle the growing volumes of waste, traditional waste management techniques frequently prove to be unsustainable and inefficient. As a result, the need for waste management systems that are more intelligent, effective, and flexible enough to meet the needs of contemporary urban areas is imperative. The utilization of smart bins—a cutting-edge trash management strategy that integrates sensor technology and real-time communication systems—is the subject of this study. With the help of numerous sensors, including fill level and cleanliness monitors, smart bins are able to collect vital information about their condition. Because these sensors are part of a strong communication network, the smart bins can send information to central databases and above all instantaneously alert local authorities via email notifications. Making use of the Internet of Things.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

We collected the previous articles from google scholar and the the Literature survey. Prakash Kanade et al [1] done a research on garbage monitoring system and reporting to the municipalities using internet of things and the methodology proposed by him dreary techinque. Limitations-Data Transmission and Connectivity. A. Krishna Kumar et al [2] done a research on Smart garbage monitoring and clearance system using internet of things and the methodology proposed by them GSM module using Iot Limitations- Data Transmission and Connectivity J. Mappillai et al [3] Meeran done a research on IOT Based Smart Garbage Monitoring System Using ZigBee methodology proposed by him Iot with the help of ZigBee. Limitations- Sensor Accuracy and reliability. Ashok Kumar et al [4] done by A Novel Approach of Using IoT Methodology for Smart Waste Management System-SIM900 . methodology proposed by him using GSM SIM-900A. Limitations-Sensor Accuracy and reliability.

III. METHODOLOGY

This paper works with the Internet of Things (IOT) to make the smartbin. This module is developed with the following requirements

A. Arduino

One popular microcontroller board that is well-known for both its simplicity and versatility is the Arduino Uno. With its digital and analog pins that are easily programmable to interface with sensors, actuators, and other electronic components, it has the ATmega328P microcontroller. It may be readily connected to a computer for programming and debugging via the Arduino IDE thanks to USB connectivity. The board has an integrated voltage regulator, so it can be powered by an external power source via USB. Because of its robust community support, large library, and open-source nature, it's a

great option for both novice and seasoned makers. It can be customized and modified for a wide range of projects, from robotics to home automation and beyond.

B. *Wifi Module*

A Wi-Fi module is a crucial part that makes it possible for devices to connect to Wi-Fi networks and provide wireless access. These modules include the related firmware or software for controlling Wi-Fi connections along with the hardware, such as antennae and connectors, required for wireless communication. Numerous technologies, such as Internet of Things (IoT) gadgets, industrial machinery, consumer electronics, and home automation systems, use Wi-Fi modules. They provide varying degrees of speed, range, and compatibility with different Wi-Fi networks while adhering to existing Wi-Fi standards. These modules' software support, power efficiency, and security features are essential components that make them adaptable and appropriate for a range of applications. Popular Wi-Fi modules are made by companies like MediaTek and Espressif, and the selection of module depends.

C. *Ultrasonic Sensor*

Ultrasonic sensors, operating on the principle of emitting and receiving high-frequency sound waves, serve as essential tools for distance measurement and object detection. These sensors emit ultrasonic waves and calculate distances by measuring the time it takes for the waves to bounce back from objects, leveraging the known speed of sound in the surrounding medium, typically air. Their key features include non-contact operation, a broad range of applications, reasonable accuracy, and versatility in various environments. Ultrasonic sensors are widely employed in robotics for object detection and avoidance, liquid level measurements in industrial settings, and parking assistance systems in vehicles. While they offer several advantages, such as simplicity and reliability, they may encounter limitations in scenarios with multiple objects or challenging surfaces. Nonetheless, ultrasonic sensors continue to be instrumental in engineering and automation tasks, providing valuable distance measurement and object detection solutions.

D. *Arduino IDE*

The Arduino IDE, short for Integrated Development Environment, is a crucial software platform for Arduino enthusiasts and developers. It provides a user-friendly interface with features like a code editor equipped with syntax highlighting and error checking, making it accessible to both beginners and experienced programmers. One of its key strengths is its support for C/C++ programming, allowing users to write and edit code for Arduino microcontroller boards. The IDE also offers a vast library of pre-written code and functions, which simplifies and accelerates project development. It includes a board manager to select the appropriate Arduino board and install the necessary board support package, ensuring compatibility and configuration. With a built-in serial monitor for real-time communication, easy code compilation, and straightforward code upload to Arduino boards via a USB connection, the Arduino IDE streamlines the development process. Being open-source and available on multiple operating systems, it fosters a vibrant community of users and developers, making it a versatile tool for creating a wide range of electronic and embedded projects.

E. *Blynk*

Blynk is a popular and versatile Internet of Things (IoT) platform that simplifies the process of building mobile applications to control and monitor connected devices. With Blynk, users can easily create custom smartphone and web applications for their IoT projects without extensive coding expertise. The platform offers a user-friendly drag-and-drop interface that allows you to design intuitive graphical user interfaces (GUIs) for controlling and visualizing data from a wide range of IoT devices, including Arduino, Raspberry Pi, ESP8266/ESP32, and more. Blynk is known for its flexibility, and it provides a powerful communication protocol that enables real-time interaction between the Blynk app and your IoT hardware. It supports various widgets and features, such as buttons, sliders, graphs, and notifications, allowing you to create interactive control panels for your projects.

IV. CIRUIT

The circuit connections are made as per the block diagram shown below.

Fig 1: Block diagram for circuit

a. *Arduino uno*

The Arduino uno is connected with the ultrasonic sensor to collect the data from it. It gives the data of the distance of the garbage is filled.

b. *Wifi Module*

The WIFI module is connected with the Arduino to analyze the data from it. It is Also connected with the Blynk app to connect with the cloud the send the mail notification from SMTP.

V. Working Model

A small prototype is designed such a way that to test the module in real time. This is a small prototype with module installed.

Fig 2: Prototype of smartbin

VI. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

A significant development in garbage disposal and environmental sustainability is the use of IoT-enabled smart bins that may send out mail notification notifications. This creative system ensures effective waste collection by using sensors and connectivity to track the bin's fill level in real-time. The responsible parties, such as waste collection teams or facility managers, receive an email notification when the bin hits a predetermined threshold, setting off an alert. With this proactive strategy, waste collection routes are optimized, which lowers fuel use and carbon emissions and eventually helps to create a cleaner, greener environment. Furthermore, it improves operational effectiveness by averting overflowing trash and related problems. The waste management industry's use of IoT and email notifications demonstrates how technology has the power to completely transform established procedures.

Fig 3: Mail notification

VII. CONCLUSION

We conclude that a smart bin system that incorporates an Arduino and a Wi-Fi module offers a strong option for improving garbage management in local governments. With the help of this technology, garbage bins with cutting-edge sensors can be filled, weighed, and environmental conditions may be monitored right away. The technology allows for prompt and effective waste collection by sending out email alerts when fill levels surpass predetermined thresholds. The usage of this technology has a number of benefits, such as lower costs, less of an impact on the environment, data-driven decision-making, scalability, and better user experiences for residents and waste collection teams. Although the given code example is meant to be a basic example, a fully functional system can be tailored to municipalities' unique requirements, promoting greener and more sustainable urban environments.

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